

VALUABLE

VALORISATION OF FUNGAL BIOMASS USING NOVEL ENZYMATIC TECHNOLOGY

Deliverable No.	D4.2
Deliverable Title	Chemically produced chitosan
Work Package No.	WP4
Work Package Title	<i>Chitin Valorization</i>
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public (PU) / <input type="checkbox"/> Sensitive (SEN)
Authors (Name, affiliation, email)	Katja Heppe, BioLog Heppe GmbH (katja.heppe@biolog-heppe.de)
Contributing partners	BioLog Heppe
Due date	31/08/2023
Submission date	31/08/2023
Version	1.0
Call ID	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CIRCBIO-01-05
Grant No.	101059786
Type of Action	IA – Innovation Actions
Start date	1 st September 2022
Final date	31 st August 2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101059786

The present deliverable has already been approved by the European Commission and has been uploaded to VALUABLE's CORDIS website: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059786>

Disclaimer

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union